

Angelo Leogrande¹

Non-Regular Employees in the Italian Regions

It grew on average in all regions by a value of 1.7 between 2004 and 2018.

Istat calculates the value of non-regular employees in the Italian regions. The variable "non-regular employees" is defined as below "*Percentage of employees who do not comply with current labor, tax and social security legislation on the total number of employees.*"

Ranking of Italian regions in 2018. In 2018, Calabria with an amount equal to 22.1%, Campania with an amount equal to 19.4%, and Sicily ranks first in the ranking of non-regular employees in the Italian regions. with a value of 18.7%. In the middle of the table there are Basilicata with a value of 14.2%, followed by Umbria with a value of 13.3% and Liguria with a value of 11.6%. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a value of 9.6%, Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of 9.4% and Veneto with a value of 9.

Variation in the percentage of non-regular employees in the Italian regions in the period between 2004 and 2018. Basilicata is in first place for the value of the variation of non-regulated employees in the Italian regions in the period between 2004 and 2018 with a value equal to 5.4, followed by Molise with a value of 5.3 and Sardinia with a value of 5. In the middle of the table there are Emilia Romagna with a value of 2, Umbria with a value of 1.9 and Friuli-Venezia Giulia with a value of 1.5%. Sicily closes the ranking with a value of 0.1, Lombardy equal to -0.4 and Campania with a value of -6.2%.

North. The percentage of non-regular employees in the North decreased in the transition between 2014 and 2018, going from a value of 10.10 to a value of 10.00 or a reduction equal to a value of 0.10 units equal to 0.99%. In the transition between 2014 and 2015, the value of non-regular employees in the North went from a value of 10.10 to a value of 10.30 units or a variation equal to a value of 0.20 units equal to an amount of 1.98%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of non-regular employees in the North decreased from a value equal to 10.30 units up to a value equal to 10.20 units or equal to a value of -0.10 units equal to a value of -0.97%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of non-regular employees increased from a value of 10.20 to a value of 10.30 units or equal to a change of 0.10 units equal to an amount of 0.98%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of non-regular employees in the North decreased from an amount equal to 10.30 to a value equal to 10.00 units or equal to a value of -0.30 units equal to an amount of -2.91%.

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

Center. The value of non-regulated employees decreased from a value of 10.60% to a value of 10.30% or a variation of 0.30 units equivalent to an amount of -2.21%. In the transition between 2014 and 2015, the value of non-regular employees in the Center remained constant at a value of 13.60. In the transition between 2015 and 2016, the value of non-regular employees decreased from a value of 13.60% to a value of 13.30% or equal to a change of -0.30 units equal to a value of -2.21%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of non-regular employees increased from an amount equal to 13.30 to a value of 13.50 units or open to a variation of 0.20 units equal to a value of 1, 50%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018 the value of non-regular employees in the Center decreased from an amount equal to 13.50 units up to a value equal to 13.30 or equal to a value of -0.20 units equal to a value of -1.48%.

South of Italy. The value of non-regular employees in the South has decreased from a value equal to 19.10 units up to a value equal to 17.90 units or a variation equal to a value of -1.20 units equal to a value of -6, 28%. In the transition between 2014 and 2015 the value of non-regular employees increased from an amount equal to 19.10 to a value equal to 19.30 or equal to a variation of 0.20 units equal to an amount of 1, 05%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016, the value of non-regular employees in the South went from a value of 19.30% to a value of 18.50% or equal to a value of -0.80 units equal to a value of -4.15%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of non-regular employees in the South decreased from an amount equal to 18.50 units up to a value of 18.30 units or equal to a variation of -0.20 units equal to a change of -1.08 units. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of non-regular employees decreased from an amount equal to 18.30 units up to a value equal to 17.90 units or equal to a value of -0.40 units equal to a value of -2.19%.

Clusterization. The clustering analysis is carried out below with the k-Means algorithm represented by the t-SNE algorithm. Based on the data analyzed, there are three clusters:

- Cluster 1: made up of Abruzzo, Basilicata, Lazio, Molise, Puglia, Sardinia, Umbria;
- Cluster 2: made up of Calabria, Campania and Sicily;
- Cluster 3: made up of Emilia-Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Liguria, Lombardy, Marche, Piedmont, Tuscany, Trentino-Alto Adige, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto.

Clustering shows that some southern regions perform better than some central regions are included in cluster 1 together with many southern regions, while in cluster 2 there are only southern regions. However, it should be considered that clustering based on the percentage of the number of non-regular workers tends to emphasize the distinction of the Italian economic structure in the three macro-regions of the center, north and south.

Conclusions. In summary, we must find that the growth of non-regular workers has occurred in all Italian regions. On average in the period between 2004 and 2018, the percentage of non-regular

workers increased by an amount equal to 1.765% except for Lombardy which recorded a -0.4 in 2018 compared to 2004 and Campania with a value of the percentage of non-regular employees which decreased by -6.2%. The growth of non-regular workers is a sign of the inefficiency of the local labor market and of the labor law legislation which, while expanding the types of contracts, evidently fails to meet the demands of labor supply and demand. A very significant role must also be recognized in the value of the tax wedge on labor which induces employers and workers to seek solutions outside the labor law system even in the informal economy.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Alberto Costantiello and Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

References

Leogrande, Angelo. Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. No. 112801. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Leogrande, Angelo. The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. No. 112954. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). *The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019* (No. 110814). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective Well-Being in Italian Regions: A Panel Data Approach. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Risk of Poverty in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6194023>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Employment Rate in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6211793>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Duration of Civil Proceedings in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6188615>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Reduction of NEETs in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6212291>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Social Participation in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6212069>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Crowding of Prisons in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395200>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*, <https://ilsudest.it/>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Road Accidents in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590888>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Graduates in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6790391>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Income Gap Between Northern and Southern Italy. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013650>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Clustering and Prediction of the Employment Rate in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013660>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Reduction of the Perception of Employment Insecurity in the Italian Regions between 2013 and 2019. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013700>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Satisfaction for the Work in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013706>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Worsening of the Condition of Women Employed with Preschool Children in the Italian Regions in the Period 2015-2019. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013718>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Reduction of Fatal Accidents and Permanent Disabilities in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013737>